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Quadratic-Exponential Distribution

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Abstract :

In this paper, we introduce a new member of family of continuous probability distributions which is based on the product of quadratic and exponential functions and hence, we named it 'Quadratic-Exponential Distribution'. Probability density function, probability distribution function and moment generating function of this distribution have been obtained. Moments about origin and hence, the first four central moments of the proposed distribution have been derived. The hazard rate function and the mean residual life function of the proposed distribution have been discussed, and show its flexibility over Lindley distribution, exponential distribution and Mishra distribution. Estimation of parameters has been discussed by the method of moments as well as the method of maximum likelihood. Goodness of fit has been applied to different data-sets which were used by others and it has been observed that it gives better fit to the most of data-sets of same nature, having variance greater than the mean, than Lindley distribution. In some cases, it gives better fit to the same nature of data-sets, having variance greater than the mean, than Mishra distribution.

Keywords : Quadratic-Exponential distribution, Lindley distribution, Parameters, Moments, Goodness of fit, Estimation.

[1]

1. Introduction:

The main objective of introducing the proposed distribution is to give a better alternative of Lindley (1958)^[2] and Mishra (2015)^[4] distributions and to create another platform for researchers working on distribution theory. It is expected that the proposed distribution will play very important role in modeling of survival time data. In the last two decades, many researchers have been published different types of Quasi-Lindley distributions having two or more than two parameters which are generalised form of Lindley distribution (1958)^[2]. Lindley introduced a one parameter continuous probability distribution, known as Lindley distribution (LD)^[2], given by its probability density function

$$f_1(x) = \frac{\phi^2(1+x)e^{-\phi x}}{(1+\phi)}; x > 0, \phi > 0 \quad (1)$$

There are very few probability distributions of single parameter which gives better fit to the same nature of datasets having variance greater than the mean. Sah (2015) introduced a one parameter continuous probability distribution, known as Mishra distribution (MD)^[4], given by its probability density function

$$f_2(x; \phi) = \frac{\phi^3}{(\phi^2 + \phi + 2)} (1+x+x^2)e^{-\phi x}; x > 0, \phi > 0 \quad (2)$$

One of them is MD of Sah (2015)^[4] which gives better fit to the same nature of data-sets, having variance greater than the mean, than LD (1958)^[2]. Sah described importance of Poisson-Mishra distribution (2017)^[5] and Generalised Poisson-Mishra distribution (2018)^[6] in accident proneness. In some cases, the proposed distribution gives better fit to the data-sets, having variance greater than the mean, than the One-Parameter Linear-exponential distribution of Sah (2021)^[7].

The r^{th} moment about origin of MD distribution was obtained by

$$\mu'_r = \frac{r! [\phi^2 + (r+1)\phi + (1+r)(2+r)]}{\phi^r (\phi^2 + \phi + 2)} \quad (3)$$

The proposed distribution is a modified form of MD (2) replacing ‘1’ by ‘ ϕ ’ in the expression $(1 + x + x^2)$ of the equation (2). The proposed distribution is based on the product of quadratic function $(\phi + x + x^2)$ and exponential function $e^{-\phi x}$ and hence, it is named as Quadratic-Exponential distribution (QED). The proposed distribution is so constructed that it follows all the basic properties of probability distribution. The different characteristics such as probability density function, probability distribution function, moment generating function, moments about origin as well as moments about the mean of the proposed distribution have been obtained. The hazard rate function and the mean residual life function of the proposed distribution have been discussed. The estimation of parameter has been discussed by the method of moments as well as the maximum likelihood methods. The proposed distribution has been fitted to some well-known data-sets which were used by others, and it is expected to give better alternative to the same nature of data-sets than LD (1) and in some cases, it gives better fit to the same nature of data-sets, having variance greater than the mean, than MD (2).

2. Results :

2.1 Quadratic-Exponential Distribution (QED) :

Quadratic-Exponential Distribution (QED) is a single parameter continuous probability distribution. It has been obtained on the basis of the product of quadratic and exponential functions. QED with parameter ϕ is defined by its probability density function (pdf)

$$f(x ; \phi) = \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} (\phi + x + x^2)e^{-\phi x} ; \text{ where } x > 0, \phi > 0 \tag{4}$$

Probability distribution function of this distribution has been obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} F(x) = P(X \leq x) &= \int_0^x f(x)dx = \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \int_0^x (\phi + x + x^2)e^{-\phi x} dx \\ &= 1 - e^{-\phi x} - \frac{\phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi x} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

4 The Mathematics Education [Vol. LVI (1), March 22]

Moment generating function (M.G.F) of the QED has been obtained by

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_X(t) = E [e^{tx}] &= \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \int_0^{\infty} (\phi + x + x^2)e^{-(\phi-t)x} dx \\
 &= \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \frac{[\phi(\phi - t)^2 + (\phi - t) + 2]}{(\phi - t)^3} \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

The expression (6) is the M.G.F. of QED (4).

Graphical representation of probability density function and distribution function for varying values of parameter are given below.

Figure 1 : Graph of pdf of QED at $\phi = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$

Figure 2 : Graph of pdf of QED at $\phi = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

Figure 3 : Graph of pdf of QED at $\phi = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$

Figure 4 : Graph of pdf of QED at $\phi = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

2.2 Moments and Related Measures of QED :

The r^{th} moment about origin of the QED (2.1) can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu'_r = E(X^r) &= \int_0^{\infty} x^r f(x) dx = \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \int_0^{\infty} x^r (\phi + x + x^2) e^{-\phi x} dx \\ &= \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \frac{\Gamma(r+1)}{\phi^{r+1}} \left[\frac{\phi}{1} + \frac{(r+1)}{\phi} + \frac{(r+1)(r+2)}{\phi^2} \right] \\ &= \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \frac{r!}{\phi^r} [\phi^3 + \phi(r+1) + (r+1)(r+2)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The expression (7) is the general form of the r^{th} moment about origin of the QED (4). Putting $r = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 in the expression (7), we get the first four moments about origin as

$$\mu'_1 = \frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{1!}{\phi} \cdot (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6) \quad (8)$$

$$\mu'_2 = \frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{2!}{\phi^2} \cdot (\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12) \quad (9)$$

$$\mu'_3 = \frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{3!}{\phi^3} \cdot (\phi^3 + 4\phi + 20) \quad (10)$$

$$\mu'_4 = \frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{4!}{\phi^4} \cdot (\phi^3 + 5\phi + 30) \quad (11)$$

The first four moments about mean of the QED (4) has been obtained as

$$\mu_1 = 0$$

$$\mu_2 = \mu'_2 - \mu'^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left[\frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{2!}{\phi^2} \cdot (\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12) \right] - \left[\frac{1}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{1!}{\phi} \cdot (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6) \right]^2 \\ &= \frac{2(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2}{\{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3)\}^2} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_3 = \mu'_3 - 3\mu'_2 \mu'_1 + 2(\mu'_1)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{6(\phi^3 + 4\phi + 20)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^2 - 6(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + 2(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^3}{\{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3)\}^3} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\mu_4 = \mu'_4 - 4\mu'_3 \mu'_1 + 6\mu'_2 (\mu'_1)^2 - 3(\mu'_1)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{24(\phi^3 + 5\phi + 30)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^3 - 24(\phi^3 + 4\phi + 20)(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^2 + 12(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - 3(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^4}{\{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3)\}^4} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We can observe that variance (12) is greater than the mean (8). Hence, QED (4) is always over-dispersed. Co-efficient of Variation [C.V.] of QED (4) can be obtained by

$$C.V = \frac{\bar{x}}{\sigma} \cdot 100 = \frac{(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)}{\sqrt{\{2(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2\}}} \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

Shape and size of the proposed probability distribution can be studied by obtaining co-efficient of skewness and kurtosis

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\left[\frac{6(\phi^3 + 4\phi + 20)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^2 - 6(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)}{(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + 2(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^3} \right]}{[2(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2]^{3/2}} \quad (16)$$

And co-efficient of kurtosis can be obtained by using

$$\beta_2 = \frac{\left[\frac{24(\phi^3 + 5\phi + 30)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^3 - 24(\phi^3 + 4\phi + 20)(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)(2 + \phi + \phi^3)^2}{+ 12(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - 3(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^4} \right]}{[2(\phi^3 + 3\phi + 12)(2 + \phi + \phi^3) - (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)^2]^2} \quad (17)$$

Here, $\gamma_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2 > 3$. Hence, QED (4) is positively skewed and leptokurtic.

2.3 The Reliability Function, Hazard Rate Function and Mean Residual Life Function :

The Reliability Function :

Let X follows QED (4) with parameter ϕ and probability density function $f(x)$. Distribution function of X is defined as

$$F(x) = 1 - e^{-\phi x} - \frac{\phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi x} = \frac{[(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi t(2 + \phi + \phi x)]}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi x}$$

Let the random variable X be the lifetime or the time to failure of a component. The probability that the component will survive until sometime 't' is called reliability $R(t)$ of the component defined by

$$R(t) = P(X > t) = \int_t^{\infty} f(x) dx = 1 - F(t) = \frac{[(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi t(2 + \phi + \phi t)]}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi t} \quad (18)$$

The component is said to be working properly at time $t = 0$ and no component work forever without failure i.e.

$$R(t = 0) = 1 \text{ and } \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} R(t) = 0$$

$R(t)$ is a monotone non-increasing function of t . For $t < 0$, the reliability has no meaning.

The Hazard Rate Function :

Hazard measures the conditional probability of a failure given that the system is working. The failure density (pdf) measures the overall speed of failures. Hazard rate or Instantaneous failure rate measures the dynamic speed of failures. For a continuous distribution with p.d.f. $f(x)$ and c.d.f. $F(x)$, the hazard rate function (also known as failure rate function) and the mean residual life function are respectively defined as

$$h(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(X < x + \Delta x / X > x)}{\Delta x} = \frac{f(x)}{1 - F(x)} \tag{19}$$

The main reason for defining the $h(x)$ is that it is more convenient to work with than $f(x)$. Putting the value of $f(x)$ and $1 - F(x)$ in the expression $h(x)$, the Hazard rate function of QED (4) has been obtained as

$$h(x) = \frac{\phi^3(\phi + x + x^2)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)} \tag{20}$$

The failure rate function of QED (4) until time ‘ t ’ is thus obtained as

$$h(x = t) = \frac{\phi^3(\phi + t + t^2)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi t(2 + \phi + \phi t)} \tag{21}$$

$$\text{At } t = 0, h(x = t = 0) = \frac{\phi^4}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \tag{22}$$

It is also obvious that $h(x)$ is an increasing function of x and ϕ .

Mean Residual Life Function :

In reliability studies, the expected additional life time given that a component has survived until time 't' is called mean residual life time. Let a random variable X denotes the life of a component, the mean residual life function is given by

$$m(x) = E[X - x | X > x] = \frac{\int_x^{\infty} [1 - F(t)] dt}{1 - F(x)} \quad (23)$$

To obtain $m(x)$ of the QED (4), we have to calculate the following measures

$$f(x; \phi, \alpha) = \frac{\phi^3}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} (\phi + x + x^2) e^{-\phi x}; x > 0, \phi > 0$$

and $F(x) = 1 - e^{-\phi x} - \frac{\phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi x}$

Where $f(x)$ and $F(x)$ are the probability density function and probability distribution function of QED (4).

$$1 - F(x) = \frac{[(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)]}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi x} \quad (24)$$

$$1 - F(t) = e^{-\phi t} + \frac{\phi t(2 + \phi + \phi t)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi t} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_x^{\infty} \{1 - F(t)\} dt &= \int_x^{\infty} \left[e^{-\phi t} + \frac{\phi t(2 + \phi + \phi t)}{(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} e^{-\phi t} \right] dt \\ &= \left[\frac{(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi(2 + 2\phi x + \phi^2 x + \phi^2 x^2) + (2\phi + \phi^2 + 2\phi^2 x)}{\phi^2(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \right] e^{-\phi x} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Putting the value of $\int_x^{\infty} [1 - F(t)] dt$ and $1 - F(x)$ in equation (23), the mean residual life function has been obtained as

$$m(x) = \frac{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi(2 + 2\phi x + \phi^2 x + \phi^2 x^2) + (2\phi + \phi^2 + 2\phi^2 x)}{\phi^2(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi x(2 + \phi + \phi x)} \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{At } x = 0, m(x = 0) &= \frac{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \phi(2) + (2\phi + \phi^2)}{\phi^2(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} \\
 &= \frac{(2 + \phi + \phi^3 + 2 + 2 + \phi)}{\phi(2 + \phi + \phi^3)} = \frac{(\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6)}{\phi(2 + \alpha\phi + \phi^3)} = \mu' \quad (28)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5 : Graph of $m(x)$ at $\phi = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$

Figure 6 : Graph of $m(x)$ at $\phi = 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$

It can also be seen that at $x = 0$, the mean residual life function is the mean of QED (4). It can also be seen that $m(x)$ is a decreasing function of x and ϕ . The hazard rate function and the mean residual life function of the QED show its flexibility over LD (1), exponential distribution and MD (2).

2.4 Stochastic Orderings :

Stochastic ordering of non-negative continuous random variables is an important tool for judging the comparative behavior. Let us consider two random variables X and Y . The random variable X is said to be smaller than Y in the

- (a) Stochastic order $(X \leq_{st} Y)$ if $F_X(x) \geq F_Y(x)$ for all x
- (b) Hazard rate order $(X \leq_{hr} Y)$ if $h_X(x) \geq h_Y(x)$ for all x
- (c) Mean residual life order $(X \leq_{mrl} Y)$ if $m_X(x) \geq m_Y(x)$ for all x
- (d) Likelihood ratio order $(X \leq_{lr} Y)$ if $\frac{f_X(x)}{f_Y(y)}$ decreases in x

The following results due to Shaked and Shanthi Kumar (1994) establishing stochastic ordering of the distributions

$$(X \leq_{lr} Y) \Rightarrow (X \leq_{hr} Y) \Rightarrow (X \leq_{mrl} Y) \Rightarrow (X \leq_{st} Y)$$

The QED (4) is ordered with respect to the strongest 'likelihood ratio' ordering as shown in the following theorem.

Theorem : Let $X \sim QED(\phi_1)$ and $Y \sim QED(\phi_2)$. If $(\phi_1 \geq \phi_2)$, then $(X \leq_{lr} Y)$ and hence $(X \leq_{hr} Y)$, $(X \leq_{mrl} Y)$ and $(X \leq_{st} Y)$.

Proof : We have

$$\frac{f_X(x)}{f_Y(x)} = \frac{\phi_1^3(2 + \phi_2 + \phi_2^3)}{\phi_2^3(2 + \phi_1 + \phi_1^3)} \frac{(\phi_1 + x + x^2)}{(\phi_2 + x + x^2)} e^{-(\phi_1 - \phi_2)x}; x > 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Or, } \log \left\{ \frac{f_X(x)}{f_Y(x)} \right\} &= \log \left\{ \frac{\phi_1^3(2 + \phi_2 + \phi_2^3)}{\phi_2^3(2 + \phi_1 + \phi_1^3)} \right\} + \log \{(\phi_1 + x + x^2)\} \\ &\quad - \log \{(\phi_2 + x + x^2)\} - (\phi_1 - \phi_2)x \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

d w.r.t. x of equation (30), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Or, } \frac{d}{dx} \log \left\{ \frac{f_X(x)}{f_Y(x)} \right\} &= \frac{(1+2x)}{(\phi_1+x+x^2)} - \frac{(1+2x)}{(\phi_2+x+x^2)} - (\phi_1 - \phi_2) \\
 &= \frac{(1+2x)(\phi_2+x+x^2) - (1+2x)(\phi_1+x+x^2)}{(\phi_1+x+x^2)(\phi_2+x+x^2)} - (\phi_1 - \phi_2) \\
 &= \frac{\phi_2+x+x^2+2\phi_2x+2x^2+2x^3 - \phi_1-x-x^2-2\phi_1x-2x^2-2x^3}{(\phi_1+\alpha_1x+x^2)(\phi_2+\alpha_2x+x^2)} - (\phi_1 - \phi_2) \\
 &= \frac{(\phi_2 - \phi_1) + 2(\phi_2 - \phi_1)x}{(\phi_1+x+x^2)(\phi_2+x+x^2)} - (\phi_1 - \phi_2) \tag{31}
 \end{aligned}$$

In the expression (31), if $\phi_1 \geq \phi_2$, then $\frac{d}{dx} \log \left\{ \frac{f_X(x)}{f_Y(x)} \right\} \leq 0$. It indicates that $(X \leq_{lr} Y)$

and hence $(X \leq_{hr} Y)$, $(X \leq_{mlr} Y)$ and $(X \leq_{st} Y)$. This theorem shows that the flexibility of the QED over Lindley and exponential distributions.

2.5 Estimation of Parameters of QED :

QED (4) has only one parameter ‘ ϕ ’. Estimate of the parameter has been obtained by using (a) Method of moments and (b) Method of maximum likelihood.

(a) Method of moments :

The proposed distribution has a single parameter ‘ ϕ ’. To estimate value of the parameter, the first moment about origin is required. So, the population mean is replaced by respective sample mean and using the expression (8), we can obtain estimate of ϕ as follows

From the expression (8), we have

$$\mu'_1 = \frac{1}{(2 + \alpha\phi + \phi^3)} \cdot \frac{1!}{\phi} \cdot (\phi^3 + 2\alpha\phi + 6)$$

After a little simplification, we get

$$f(\phi) = \mu'_1 (\phi^4 + \phi^2 + 2\phi) - (\phi^3 + 2\phi + 6) = 0 \tag{32}$$

The expression (32) is the polynomial in fourth degree equation. Replacing the corresponding population mean by respective sample mean and solving the expression (32) by using Regula-Falsi method, we get an estimate of ϕ .

(b) The method of maximum likelihood :

Let $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be a random sample of size n from QED (4) and let f_x be the observed frequency in the sample corresponding to $X=x$ ($x = 1, 2, \dots, k$) such that $\sum_{x=1}^k f_x = n$, where k is the largest observed value having non-zero frequency. The likelihood function L , of the QED (4) is obtained as

$$L = \left(\frac{\phi^3}{2 + \phi + \phi^3} \right)^n \prod_{x=1}^k (\phi + x + x^2)^{f_x} e^{-n\phi\bar{x}} \tag{33}$$

and so, the log likelihood function is obtained as

Or,
$$\ln L = 3n \ln \phi - n \ln(2 + \phi + \phi^3) + \sum_{x=1}^k f_x \ln(\phi + x + x^2) - n\phi\bar{x} \tag{34}$$

The log likelihood equation is thus obtained as

Or,
$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \phi} = \frac{3n}{\phi} - \frac{n(1 + 3\phi^2)}{(2 + \alpha\phi + \phi^3)} + \sum_{x=1}^k \frac{f_x}{(\phi + x + x^2)} - n\bar{x} = 0 \tag{35}$$

We can observe that the equation (35) does not seem to be solved directly. However, Fisher’s scoring method can be applied to solve this equation.

2.6 Goodness of Fit :

The QED (4) has been fitted to a number of data-sets to which earlier the Lindley distribution has been fitted by others and to almost all these data-sets this distribution provides closer fits than the Lindley distribution. The fittings of the QED to the two such data-sets have been presented in the following tables. The first data-set is regarding the survival times (in days) of guinea pigs infected with virulent tubercle bacilli, observed and reported by Bzerkedal (1960)^[1], and the

second data-set is regarding mortality grouped data for blackbirds species, reported by Paranjpe and Rajarshi (1986)^[3]. The expected frequencies according to the Lindley distribution, and Mishra distributions have also been given for ready comparison with those obtained by the QED.

Table - 1

Survival times (in days) of 72 guinea pigs infected with virulent tubercle bacilli

Survival Time (in days)	Observed frequency	Expected frequency		
		Lindley	Mishra	QED
0-80	8	16.1	10.8	10.8
80-160	30	21.9	24.8	24.8
160-240	18	15.4	19.0	19.0
240-320	8	9.0	10.1	10.1
320-400	4	5.5	4.5	4.5
400-480	3	1.8	1.8	1.8
480-560	1	2.3	1.0	1.0
Total	72	72.0	72.0	72.0
$\hat{\phi}$		0.011	0.016431	0.016519
$\chi^2(df)$		7.7712(3)	1.98(3)	1.98(3)
$\mu'_1 = 181.11111$		$\mu'_2 = 43911.11111$		

The expected frequencies according to the LD (1), and MD (2) have also been given for ready comparison with those obtained by the QED. From table - 1, we can observe that the value of Chi-square of QED is less than the Lindley distribution and is equal to the Mishra distribution with same degrees of freedom. From table - 2, we can observe that the value of Chi-square of QED is less than Lindley as well as Mishra distributions. Hence, it may conclude that in most of the cases QED gives better fit to the same nature of data-sets than Lindley distribution and in some cases, it gives better fit than the Mishra distribution.

Table - 2

Mortality grouped data for blackbirds species reported
by Paranjpe and Rajarshi (1986)

Survival Time (in days)	Observed frequency	Expected frequency		
		Lindley	Mishra	QED
0-1	192	173.5	142.8	145.9
1-2	60	98.6	104.5	101.2
2-3	50	46.5	58.7	57.6
3-4	20	20.1	27.5	27.5
4-5	12	8.1	11.5	12.0
5-6	7	3.2	4.5	4.8
6-7	6	1.4	1.6	1.8
7-8	3	0.4	0.5	0.7
>8	2	0.3	0.4	0.5
Total	352	352.0	352.0	352.0
$\hat{\phi}$		.984	1.311017	1.269721
$\chi^2(df)$		49.85(4)	46.37(4)	39.64
$\mu'_1 = 1.56818$		$\mu'_2 = 5.005682$		

3. Conclusion :

In this paper, we propose a single parameter continuous distribution which is named as Quadratic-Exponential Distribution (QED). Several structural properties such as moment generating function, distribution function, moments about origin as well as the mean have been derived. The reliability function, hazard rate function and mean residual life function have been obtained and discussed. The methods of estimation of parameter have been discussed. Finally, the proposed distribution has been fitted to a number of data-sets, having variance greater than the mean, to test its goodness of fit and it has been observed that the QED (4) gives better fit to the

most of the similar nature of the data-sets than the Lindley distribution and in some cases, it gives better fit than Mishra distribution. It is expected that it will be very useful for betterment in modeling of life time data as shown in above tables.

Conflict of Interest :

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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